

Esophageal perforation in an 80-year-old patient following transesophageal echocardiography: A case report

Gabriella NUCERA^{1*}, Giovanna PETAZZI², Francesco CAVALERI³, Marina MOLGORA⁴,
Andrea BERETTA⁵

MD, Fatebenefratelli Hospital, Milano, Italy. E-mail: gabriellanucera@gmail.com. ORCID: 0000-0003-1425-0046

MD, Fatebenefratelli Hospital, Milano, Italy. E-mail: giovanna.petazzi@asst-fbf-sacco.it

MD, Fatebenefratelli Hospital, Milano, Italy. E-mail: francesco.cavaleri@asst-fbf-sacco.it

MD, Fatebenefratelli Hospital, Milano, Italy. E-mail: marina.molgora@asst-fbf-sacco.it

MD, Fatebenefratelli Hospital, Milano, Italy. E-mail: andrea.beretta@asst-fbf-sacco.it

*Correspondence

Cite this paper as:

Nucera G, Petazzi G, Cavaleri F, Molgora M, Beretta A. Esophageal perforation in an 80-year-old patient following transesophageal echocardiography: A case report. *Adv Med Psychol Public Health*. 2024;1(1):47-50.
Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10598881

Received: 02 November 2023

Revised: 15 December 2023

Accepted: 04 January 2024

Abstract

We report a rare case of esophageal perforation in an 80-year-old female patient following transesophageal echocardiography (TEE). This procedure was imperative for evaluating the presence of thrombi in the right atrial appendage before an endoscopic closure of the appendage, particularly due to her history of atrial fibrillation and recent cerebral hemorrhage while on anticoagulant therapy. This case highlights the inherent risks associated with TEE, especially in the elderly with complicating factors such as osteophytic changes and a history of anticoagulation, but also underscores the importance of thorough pre-procedural assessment and careful monitoring. Our findings align with the literature, emphasizing the elevated risk of esophageal injury in elderly patients during TEE and the need for heightened vigilance in this population.

Take-home message: The case of esophageal perforation in an elderly patient following transesophageal echocardiography underscores the critical need for comprehensive pre-procedural evaluation and cautious monitoring, particularly in older adults with complex medical histories. This report highlights the importance of considering age and specific health conditions as significant risk factors for complications during invasive cardiac procedures.

Keywords: atrial appendage closure; case report; esophageal perforation; elderly; transesophageal echocardiography.

INTRODUCTION

Esophageal perforation, recognized as a possible yet significant complication of transesophageal echocardiography (TEE), has been documented in medical literature as a serious concern [1,2]. We present a case examining a specific instance of esophageal injury following TEE. This report contributes to the growing knowledge of TEE's safe and effective use, particularly in patients with higher risk profiles, by exploring the clinical context, management strategies, and implications of such complications.

CASE DESCRIPTION

The patient, an 80-year-old female with a medical history significant for atrial fibrillation, was scheduled for a transesophageal echocardiography (TEE) examination. This procedure was crucial as a preoperative assessment for the proposed endoscopic closure of her right atrial appendage. The closure was deemed necessary due to her history of atrial fibrillation, which had been complicated by a recent fall resulting in cerebral hemorrhage. Additionally, the patient was on anticoagulant therapy to manage her atrial fibrillation, increasing her stroke risk and necessitating the closure procedure.

At the time of the TEE, the patient was conscious with stable vital signs. However, her recent cerebral hemorrhage and ongoing anticoagulation therapy presented unique challenges and risks for the procedure. The TEE was vital in determining the suitability for the atrial appendage closure, a common intervention to reduce stroke risk in patients with atrial fibrillation.

During the TEE, the patient was under conscious sedation. The procedure was initially reported as uneventful. However, within a few hours post-examination, the patient began to experience severe symptoms indicative of a possible esophageal injury. He complained of acute onset of chest pain, radiating to the back, and dysphagia, indicating difficulty in swallowing, both of which are not typical for him. The chest pain was described as sharp and worsened with swallowing movements.

Given these symptoms, the medical team promptly initiated a diagnostic workup. A computed tomography (CT) scan of the chest was performed, which revealed the presence of air and fluid collection around the esophageal region, indicative of an esophageal perforation. Additionally, there was evidence of mediastinal widening, a common complication of esophageal perforation due to the spread of esophageal contents into the mediastinum.

The patient was immediately started on broad-spectrum intravenous antibiotics to prevent infection, and nil per os (NPO) status was initiated to rest the esophagus. Surgical consultation was sought, and the patient was taken to the operating room for an emergency surgical perforation repair. A thorough examination of the esophagus during surgery confirmed the presence of a perforation in the mid-thoracic esophagus.

Post-surgical management was critical for this patient due to his advanced age and the complexity of the esophageal injury. The patient was closely monitored in the intensive care unit (ICU) postoperatively. Nutritional support was initially managed with enteral feeding through a nasogastric tube, followed by a gradual reintroduction of oral intake once the esophagus was healed on follow-up imaging and endoscopy.

This case highlights the importance of recognizing the potential risks associated with TEE, especially in the elderly population. Despite the relative rarity of esophageal perforation following TEE, its occurrence necessitates prompt diagnosis and intervention to minimize morbidity and mortality associated with this severe complication.

DISCUSSION

Esophageal perforation as a consequence of transesophageal echocardiography (TEE) is an uncommon but grave complication. Herbold and colleagues retrospectively reviewed all patients treated for esophageal perforation and included all patients with perforation caused by TEE. They found that "in 6 patients (5.5%), the perforation was caused by TEE" and "all patients underwent successful endoscopic treatment." All patients underwent successful endoscopic treatment, and no further surgical procedure, such as esophageal suture or resection, was necessary. They showed how esophageal perforations caused by TEE are typically small in the cervical and mid esophagus and minimally contaminated and the potential for successful management through endoscopic treatment [3]. The systematic review by Sainathan & Andaz [4] on transesophageal echocardiography (TEE)-induced esophageal perforation showed two key points: firstly, that TEE-induced esophageal perforation typically occurs in elderly female patients, predominantly in an intra-operative setting, and secondly, that the majority of these perforations occur in the thoracic esophagus, especially during intra-operative TEE procedures. In literature, some large retrospective trials suggested that patient factors (age, body mass index, anatomic abnormalities), comorbid conditions (previous stroke), and procedural variables (procedure time, cardiopulmonary bypass time, etc.) are associated with TEE-related injuries [5].

These findings are particularly relevant to our case report, underscoring the demographic and procedural contexts in which such complications most frequently arise. While cases of TEE-induced esophageal perforation in the elderly are not extensively reported in the literature, their clinical significance is profound. Age-related changes in esophageal tissue integrity, as well as pre-existing medical conditions, can substantially increase the vulnerability of older patients to such injuries.

For instance, Bavalia and colleagues [6] reported a case of esophageal perforation in a 77-year-old woman undergoing TEE, where chronic steroid therapy for asthma symptoms and osteophytic changes of the cervical vertebrae were identified as contributing factors to her increased risk of perforation. This case, among others, highlights the importance of a thorough pre-procedural assessment of the elderly. It is crucial to consider not just age but also the presence of comorbidities and other risk factors that might predispose an individual to esophageal trauma during TEE.

In discussing the role of age as a risk factor for esophageal perforation during transesophageal echocardiography (TEE), it's important to consider the findings of Royer et al. in their 2020 study [5]. Their case report and literature review, focusing on an elderly patient with prominent vertebral osteophytes who experienced esophageal perforation following TEE, highlight the increased risk in older patients. The study underscores that age-related anatomical changes, such as the presence of vertebral osteophytes, can contribute to the complexity and risk of TEE procedures. This finding is particularly relevant to our case report involving an 80-year-old patient. It suggests that elderly patients may have unique anatomical and physiological characteristics predisposing them to complications during invasive procedures like TEE. The study by Royer et al. (2020) supports the notion that advanced age and specific age-related conditions should be considered significant risk factors when planning and conducting TEE [7].

Therefore, this case emphasizes the need for a comprehensive evaluation of TEE's risks and benefits in elderly patients, especially those with known risk factors for esophageal injury. It underscores the importance of individualized patient care, where decisions regarding procedures like TEE are made considering the unique health profiles of elderly patients. The management of esophageal perforation requires a swift and coordinated approach, as demonstrated in our case. Prompt surgical intervention was crucial in addressing the esophageal tear, followed by comprehensive postoperative care. This care included antibiotic therapy to prevent infection and tailored nutritional support, initially via enteral feeding, to ensure adequate healing and recovery. Regular follow-up with endoscopies and imaging studies was essential in monitoring the patient's progress and detecting any potential complications at an early stage. Despite the age-related challenges and the urgency of the surgical intervention, our patient exhibited a notably positive recovery trajectory, without significant long-term complications. This outcome can be attributed to the prompt recognition of the perforation, the immediate surgical response, and the meticulous postoperative management.

Our case highlights the importance of vigilance during TEE, especially considering the subtle nature of symptoms that may initially manifest in cases of esophageal injury. Early detection and management are key to preventing severe morbidity and mortality. Furthermore, this case emphasizes the need for enhanced awareness among clinicians regarding the potential risks of TEE in the elderly. It also calls for developing and implementing strategies to minimize these risks, possibly including refined procedural techniques, the use of protective measures, and the selection of alternative diagnostic modalities when appropriate.

In conclusion, while esophageal perforation following TEE is a rare occurrence, it is a serious complication that warrants consideration, especially in older patients. Our experience with this case reinforces the necessity for continuous vigilance, rapid intervention in the face of complications, and a multidisciplinary approach to care to ensure the best possible outcomes for patients undergoing TEE.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this case report underscores the critical need for heightened vigilance and individualized care in managing elderly patients undergoing transesophageal echocardiography (TEE). It highlights the importance of considering both age

and comorbidities as risk factors for esophageal perforation. In this case, the successful outcome achieved through prompt recognition and appropriate management demonstrates the possibility of favorable recovery, even in complex scenarios. This case reminds healthcare professionals to remain cautious and proactive in identifying and mitigating potential risks associated with diagnostic procedures in the elderly population.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization: GN; investigation: GN, GP, FC, MM; writing—original draft preparation: GN; writing—review and editing, GP, FC, MM; supervision: AB; project administration: AB. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Acknowledgments: None

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The Publisher remains neutral regarding jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations. Additionally, the Publisher is not responsible for the accuracy, completeness, or validity of the content of scientific articles published herein. This statement exempts the Publisher from any responsibility regarding the content of scientific articles, which is solely the responsibility of the authors and peer reviewers.

References

1. Szyszka A, Płońska-Gościński E. Transesophageal echocardiography. *J Ultrason*. 2019;19(76):62-65. doi: 10.15557/JoU.2019.0009.
2. Iriarte F, Riquelme GA, Sorensen P, Pirchi DE, Mihura Iribarra M. Esophageal perforation after transesophageal echocardiography: A case report. *Int J Surg Case Rep*. 2020;66:21-24. doi: 10.1016/j.ijscr.2019.11.020. Epub 2019 Nov 19.
3. Herbold T, Chon SH, Grimminger P, Maus MKH, Schmidt H, Fuchs H, et al. Endoscopic Treatment of Transesophageal Echocardiography-Induced Esophageal Perforation. *J Laparoendosc Adv Surg Tech A*. 2018 Apr;28(4):422-428. doi: 10.1089/lap.2017.0559. Epub 2018 Jan 12.
4. Sainathan S, Andaz S. A systematic review of transesophageal echocardiography-induced esophageal perforation. *Echocardiography*. 2013 Sep;30(8):977-983. doi: 10.1111/echo.12290. Epub 2013 Jul 9.
5. Patel KM, Desai RG, Trivedi K, Neuburger PJ, Krishnan S, Potestio CP. Complications of Transesophageal Echocardiography: A Review of Injuries, Risk Factors, and Management. *J Cardiothorac Vasc Anesth*. 2022 Aug;36(8 Pt B):3292-3302. doi: 10.1053/j.jvca.2022.02.015. Epub 2022 Feb 12.
6. Bavalia N, Anis A, Benz M, Maldjian P, Bolanowski PJ, Saric M. Esophageal perforation, the most feared complication of TEE: early recognition by multimodality imaging. *Echocardiography*. 2011 Mar;28(3):E56-9. doi: 10.1111/j.1540-8175.2010.01291.x. Epub 2011 Mar 3.
7. Royer O, Couture ÉJ, Nicodème F, Kalavrousiotis D, Maruyama TC, Denault A, et al. Esophageal Perforation with Transesophageal Echocardiography in an Elderly Patient with Prominent Vertebral Osteophytes: A Case Report and a Review of the Literature. *CASE (Phila)*. 2020 Jul 25;4(5):331-336. doi: 10.1016/j.case.2020.06.006.

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Submitted for possible open-access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative

Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).